

16th International Workshop on Document Analysis Systems 2024

Short Papers

30th & 31st of August 2024, Athens, Greece

Preface

We are delighted to welcome you to the Sixteenth IAPR International Workshop on Document Analysis Systems (DAS 2024). Athens is the perfect place to carry on the rich tradition of past DAS workshops, extending from Kaiserslautern, Germany (1994); Malvern, PA, USA (1996); Nagano, Japan (1998); Rio de Janeiro, Brazil (2000); Princeton, NJ, USA (2002); Florence, Italy (2004); Nelson, New Zealand (2006); Nara, Japan (2008); Boston, MA, USA (2010); Gold Coast, Australia (2012); Tours - Loire Valley, France (2014); Santorini, Greece (2016); Wien, Austria (2018); Wuhan, China (2020) and La Rochelle, France (2022).

As with previous DAS workshops, the 2024 edition maintains a focus on system-level issues and approaches in document analysis and recognition. The big change for this year is that DAS is from now on organized in conjunction with its bigger "brother", the International Conference on Document Analysis and Recognition (ICDAR). Still, DAS remains distinct from the other ICDAR workshops, as it is published in its own separate proceedings and is by far the biggest workshop; it covers two days, a multi-thematic programme, and the largest number of submissions. We have worked hard to keep DAS a great workshop, and took care to deliver a single-track, rigorously peer-reviewed and 100% participation event that comprises invited talks, contributed papers and discussion groups.

Practitioners, theorists, industry researchers, and academics from various disciplines are brought together in DAS, all focused on the latest advancements in document analysis systems. This year, we have announced two separate calls for papers, the earlier one corresponding to "long" papers that will be included in the proceedings, and the other one for short papers that represent preliminary works or brief reports of research-in-progress. Of the 43 submissions received in an open call for papers, 27 were accepted for presentation at the workshop (acceptance ratio: 62%). Both long and short papers received rigorous peer reviewing, and meta-reviewed by the organizing committee. Of the 5 short papers received, all 5 were accepted for poster presentation at the workshop (acceptance ratio: 100%). The accepted regular papers are published in this proceedings volume in the Springer Lecture Notes in Computer Science series. Short papers appear in PDF form on the DAS conference website.

The majority of submissions received two reviews from our team of 57 Program Committee members. The final program includes four oral sessions and discussion groups. We deeply thank everyone who dedicated their time and effort to making DAS 2024 a premier event for the community. The success of the workshop program was indeed due to the efforts of many individuals. We sincerely thank the Program Committee members for their hard work reviewing submissions, and especially those last-minute, emergency reviewers that were instrumental in avoiding notification delays (we owe you a beer or two in Athens!). We are grateful to all the organizing committee team regardless of their special

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role. We thank the general chairs Muhammad Zeshan Afzal and Faisal Shafait for our seamless cooperation, and the publicity chair, Michael Coustaty, for his invaluable assistance in securing sponsorship for the workshop. Special thanks to Momina Moetesum for creating and maintaining the DAS website, and the publication chairs, Vincent Christlein and Mathias Seuret, for their work on overseeing the proceedings.

Lastly, we extend our gratitude to the authors for their excellent contributions and participation in DAS 2024. We hope this program inspires further research and provides practitioners with enhanced techniques, algorithms, and tools. It is our honor and privilege to share the latest advancements in document analysis systems with you through these proceedings.

August 2024

George Retsinas
Giorgos Sfikas

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A collaborative platform for the segmentation and transcription of historical texts

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Abstract. The "Lettres en Lumières" project aims to create a collaborative platform dedicated to the transcription and segmentation of historical documents. This platform has enabled the annotation of the DRoSB base, which combines manual segmentation data for training object recognition models, such as Mask-RCNN, and transcription data initially obtained through semi-automatic processes.

Correction of the transcriptions, performed by volunteers and validated by professional palaeographers, ensures the accuracy and reliability of the data. The platform offers several interfaces to manage these tasks, including segmentation correction, transcription, transcription validation, and management.

In addition, "Lettres en Lumières" uses the IIIF format to publish the results and allow for a wide dissemination of the transcribed documents. This format facilitates the sharing and visualization of high-resolution images and textual and graphical annotations.

The project has been designed with a multi-tenant architecture that guarantees the autonomy and confidentiality of each partner institution, while allowing the platform to be continuously updated to meet users' needs.

Keywords: Historical documents · Collaboration · IIIF · Document layout analysis · Handwritten Text recognition · Image Segmentation · Digital platform.

1 Introduction

The "Lettres en Lumières" project is part of a dynamic effort to promote and preserve the documentary heritage. In collaboration with the Departmental Archives of Côte d'Or and other partners, this project aims to facilitate access to historical documents through an innovative platform dedicated to automatique text transcription and segmentation.

The "Lettres en Lumières" platform was initially developed to create the Deliberation Registers of the States of Burgundy (DRoSB) [1] database, which includes essential segmentation and transcription data for training artificial neural network's based object recognition models such as Mask-RCNN [3][2], as well as for the creation of textual corpora for research in the humanities and social sciences. These data are generated by a combination of manual and semi-automatic processes to ensure both accuracy and speed of transcription.

In order to guarantee the quality of the transcriptions, the platform integrates several levels of correction and validation. Volunteer palaeographers correct the automated transcriptions before they are validated by professional palaeographers, thus ensuring high reliability of the data produced. In addition, the publication of the transcribed documents is done using the IIIF (International Image Interoperability Framework) format, promoting international sharing and increased accessibility for researchers and the general public.

"Lettres en Lumières" is characterized by a multi-tenant architecture, which ensures the autonomy and confidentiality of partner institutions while allowing for continuous customization and adaptation to user needs. By providing a user-friendly interface and various management tools, the project aims to optimize the collaboration between volunteer paleographers, archivists, and researchers, while promoting the preservation and study of historical documents.

2 Collaborative Platform

The DRoSB Base is a valuable resource that combines both segmentation and transcription data. This data is essential for training object recognition models such as Mask-RCNN, as well as for creating text corpora for research in the humanities and social sciences. The distinction between the two types of data, segmentation and transcription, is crucial to ensure the quality and accuracy of the results obtained.

The segmentation data used to train models like Mask-RCNN is manually generated. This process requires human expertise to accurately delineate the contours of objects present in the images, which is essential to ensure model performance and generalization.

On the other hand, the segments used exclusively for transcription are obtained semi-automatically. First, the pages are automatically segmented and transcribed using image processing and Optical Character Recognition (OCR) algorithms. However, these automatic transcriptions can contain errors or inconsistencies, especially in the case of old or damaged documents.

Therefore, a manual correction step is necessary to obtain a "sufficient" segmentation mask for transcription. Volunteer paleographers are responsible for checking and correcting the automatic transcriptions by comparing the text extracted from the images with the text actually present on the documents. This correction step is crucial to ensure the accuracy and reliability of the data transcribing the content of the documents.

Once the transcriptions have been reviewed and corrected by volunteer contributors, they are submitted for final validation by professional paleographers. This validation ensures the scientific quality of the data produced and its compliance with current academic standards.

To facilitate and optimize this complex process of transcribing historical documents, the collaborative platform LettresEnLumieres was developed by one of the co-authors (R. Lefèvre). It offers a user-friendly and intuitive interface for data annotation, as well as a task management system that allows tracking and coordinating the work of volunteer contributors and the staff of the Departmental Archives using the platform.

Fig. 1. List of pages to correct

Fig. 2. Interface of segmentation and transcription correction

Fig. 3. Validation interface

Fig. 4. Dashboard

Fig. 5. Automatic transcription, segmentation and upload interface

The platform is organized around five distinct interfaces:

1. **Segmentation Correction Interface:** Shown in Figure 1 and 2 this interface allows for precise delineation of the text areas to be transcribed when the masks lack precision or the segmentation model has made errors. The masks are represented as polygons, allowing the user to add and delete masks as well as add, delete, or move points. For adding points, this interface supports a pen, which simplifies the outlining of large volumes of lines.
2. **Transcription Correction Interface:** Provides an ergonomic and interactive environment for entering and correcting the text automatically transcribed by the OCR model. This interface is the same as the segmentation interface shown in figure 1 and 2, except that this interface does not allow the addition of masks. It is divided into two main parts:
 - **Left:** The digitized document, where each line of text is highlighted by a segmentation mask. The user can navigate through the document, zoom in on specific areas, and directly select a line for correction.
 - **Right:** The transcription corresponding to each line of text, automatically generated by the OCR. The user can modify this transcription, adding missing characters, or correcting recognition errors.
3. **Transcription Validation Interface:** Illustrated in Figure 3 and 1 This critical interface ensures the quality control of the transcriptions made by volunteer paleographers. It is accessible to professional paleographers and to experienced volunteers called "trusted validators." Coordinated by one of the co-authors (M. Llorca), these experts meticulously check each transcription for accuracy, consistency with the original document, and adherence to established transcription standards. In particular, they ensure:
 - Correct spelling and grammar;
 - Fidelity to the spelling and idioms of the document's period;
 - Correct identification of abbreviations and symbols;
 In case of doubt or difficulty, the validators can directly consult the original digitized document, zoom in on specific areas, and compare the transcription with the handwritten text.

If a transcription is deemed unsatisfactory or incomplete, several actions can be taken:

 - **Direct correction:** The validator can make the necessary corrections.
 - **Return to the volunteer contributor:** The transcription is sent back to the initial volunteer paleographer for correction based on the validator's comments.
 - **Reassignment:** If the document presents particular difficulties (old handwriting, degraded state, Latin, etc.), it may be reassigned to a volunteer with more appropriate expertise.

This rigorous validation step ensures the quality of the transcriptions produced by *Lettres en Lumières*, thereby increasing the value and reliability of the database for model training, research, and future use.

4. **Administrator Interface:** This interface provides a comprehensive set of tools for managing and monitoring all activities on the Lettres en Lumières platform. It is reserved for project administrators, who have a global view and precise control over the various aspects of the platform.

The main features of the administrator interface are as follows:

- **User Management:** Creating, modifying and deleting user accounts (volunteer contributors, professional paleographers, administrators), assigning roles and permissions that provide access to different interfaces and functionalities of the platform.
- **Progress Tracking:** Real-time visualization of the progress of transcription projects illustrated in figure 4 with five distinct states: Segmentation to be validated, Page to be assigned, Page assigned, Pages suspended, Pages to be validated. Tracking of pages assigned to volunteer contributors, identification of any blockages or delays.
- **Detailed Statistics:** Statistics on the different registers: Number of pages and their status, number of pages transcribed by each contributor. In the future, error rates per character will be tracked for each register for each version of the model.
- **Document Management:** Adding, deleting, and organizing the documents to be transcribed. For each document, the inventory created by the archives service is associated. This interface also allows documents to be assigned to contributors according to their skills and availability.

The administrator interface is designed to be intuitive and easy to use, even for non-technical users. It allows administrators to efficiently manage the Lettres en Lumières project, ensure the quality of the data produced, and optimize collaboration between the various parties involved.

5. **Automatic Document Transcription Interface:** Once the documents have been created in the administrator interface, it is possible to upload digitized pages (see figure 5) that will be segmented, transcribed, and automatically associated with the correct documents. These pages go directly into the correction process with the status "Segmentation to be verified".

Each contributor, whether a volunteer or a member of the archives staff, has access only to a specific part of the interface, thus ensuring the security and confidentiality of the data and limiting unnecessary information in each user's interface.

Lettres en Lumières is a project in constant evolution. The interfaces are regularly updated based on user feedback and project progress. Each milestone allows for the integration of more people and parts of the transcription chain, which requires a continuous adaptation of the platform to meet new needs.

In a logic of compartmentalization and customization, the application is designed with a multi-tenant architecture. Each archives service has its own instance of the application, with its own database and user accounts. This approach guarantees the autonomy and confidentiality of each partner institution.

It also ensures the publication of data on an IIIF server, in accordance with the international protocol for the sharing and visualization of cultural data, thus

promoting the work done and making it accessible to a wide audience of researchers and amateur historians.

3 IIIF Site

The need to publish the first results of the *Lettres en Lumières* project quickly became apparent. This publication will both highlight the work of the team of volunteer contributors and reach the widest possible audience, a stated goal of the Departmental Archives of Côte d’Or, the project’s promoter. The project internally uses its own JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) sharing format, which cannot be used for publication. The National Archives of France promote the IIIF, International Image Interoperability Framework format, in particular through the *iiif360* teams of the Condorcet campus. Many French and international archives already share their collections in this format. The IIIF format is initially a high-resolution image sharing format but also allows for graphic annotations (SVG (Scalable Vector Graphics) format) that can be used for segmentation and textual annotations for transcriptions.

We have therefore added a publication function to the collaborative platform specifically designed for *Lettres en Lumières*, to a IIIF server, developed for the project and, unlike the collaborative platform, open to the public. Validated pages can be sent directly to the IIIF server. We have also made it possible for anyone who wishes to contribute to the project to correct the annotations of the IIIF manifests directly after registering. The *Lettres en Lumières* IIIF server uses the Presentation and Image APIs (Application Programming Interfaces) in version 3.0 of the IIIF format. The Authentication and Search APIs are not used. The project’s IIIF site provides a textual search tool in the published volumes. The manifests are enriched with metadata automatically extracted from the inventories of the Departmental Archives (xml-ead format). This processing chain is described in the following figure 3

Some archives, such as the Departmental Archives of Hérault, already publish manuscripts on a IIIF server, but only as images. The *Lettres en Lumières* project aims to enrich the existing manifests with their transcriptions.

4 Conclusion

Lettres en Lumières aims to facilitate the enhancement of documentary heritage. By developing an intuitive and modular collaborative platform, this project combines the efforts of volunteers, professionals, and the use of artificial intelligence to produce high quality transcriptions of historical documents. Through the use of the DRoSB Base and advanced object recognition models such as Mask-RCNN, along with rigorous correction and validation processes, the data generated is both accurate and reliable.

The adoption of the IIIF format for the publication of transcribed documents increases the impact of the project by facilitating the sharing and visualization of data on an international scale. This approach allows for the recognition of contributors' work and makes historical documents accessible to a wide audience of researchers and history enthusiasts.

The platform's multi-tenant architecture ensures the autonomy and confidentiality of partner institutions while providing ongoing flexibility and adaptability. In this way, Lettres en Lumières demonstrates how technology and collaboration can be put at the service of cultural heritage, opening up new possibilities for research in the humanities and social sciences.

Lettres en Lumières is a nice example of how technological innovation can support and enrich the preservation and dissemination of documentary heritage, while fostering effective collaboration between different stakeholders. This project can inspire other national Archives services by providing a solid foundation for new initiatives.

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Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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OCR4all 1.0 – Flexible open-source OCR/HTR based on various single-step Solutions

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Abstract. Recent progress in Automatic Text Recognition (ATR) has been bolstered by the continuous release of open-source implementations addressing individual steps of the workflow. Since the optimal approach varies depending on the material at hand and individual quality requirements, we argue that the next crucial step is the establishment of user-friendly software that facilitate flexible, integrative, and sustainable combinations of current and future solutions. To this end, we introduce the fully reworked OCR4all which empowers even non-technical users to independently perform ATR achieving high-quality results. OCR4all is 100% open-source and integrates a variety of solutions, ensuring that users can leverage the best tools available for their specific needs.

Keywords: practical OCR/HTR · gui-based tool · open-source.

1 Introduction

Due to various challenges in ATR for printed and handwritten material, great progress has been made during the last decade regarding the actual text recognition step but also in layout analysis, and pre- and postprocessing. Additionally, free open-source implementations of related tools and algorithms are released constantly. These allow tackling highly heterogeneous use-cases ranging from mass full-text digitization in libraries and archives to the high-quality transcription of challenging printings and manuscripts often by non-technical users, including specific Ground Truth (GT) production and documents-specific training.

These scenarios call for a targeted deployment of specialized solutions for the steps in an ATR workflow as the optimal approach can vary considerably. Consequently, we argue that the next important step is the (further) establishment of easy-to-use frameworks that allow for a flexible, connectable, and sustainable combination as well as the application of current and future individual technical solutions. Therefore, we introduce the fully reworked open-source software OCR4all¹ that aims at enabling any given user to perform ATR completely on their own and in great quality. To achieve this, OCR4all relies on open-source tools made accessible via an intuitive GUI which also allows to view and edit the automatically produced results at any stage of the workflow.

¹ <https://www.ocr4all.org> (will be updated regarding the new version shortly)

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: In Sec. 2 we address notable Related Work. Sec. 3 covers the philosophy of OCR4all and its legacy version before Sec. 4 introduces its completely reworked version 1.0. Typical ways of working with OCR4all are covered in Sec. 5 before Sec. 6 concludes the paper.

2 Related Work

In this chapter we take a brief look at some of the numerous ATR solutions. First, we focus on command line based tools before turning to GUI-based ones and platforms. While our main focus clearly lies on open-source solutions, we also include some proprietary ones.

2.1 Command line based solution

There are a variety of almost exclusively command line based tools that cover the main steps of a complete ATR workflow: This includes the somewhat outdated but still fairly useful **OCRopus** [1,2], the regularly updated **Tesseract** [13] with its unprecedented speed when solely relying on the CPU and its very comprehensive model repository for modern fonts, and **Kraken** [4] which is originally based on OCRopus but has since been greatly expanded, most importantly by fundamentally new implementation of a fully trainable layout analysis [5]. Beyond this, there are a variety of open-source solutions that focus on a single step of the workflow, among others **Eynollah** [12] for layout analysis or **Calamari** [15], **PyLaia** [9], or the transformer-based **TrOCR** [7] for text recognition.

Each of the systems mentioned so far have different strengths and weaknesses in relation to individual sub-steps, which is why a combining them makes sense. The DFG-funded **OCR-D** [8] funding initiative addresses this task by ensuring the interoperability of several single-task processors including many of the aforementioned solutions resulting in a high degree of flexibility, future-proofness, and sustainability. The software is fully open-source and the Python API can be directly accessed in other Python scripts and is exposed via the CLI.

2.2 GUI-based solutions and platforms

Several systems provide automatic solutions for layout analysis and text recognition as well as a suitable GUI-based correction interfaces and the possibility to train new models: Commercial platforms include **Transkribus** [3] and **Teklia**², whose sub-modules mainly are proprietary and closed-source, among others hindering the reuse of trained models outside the respective platforms, while also raising questions regarding data sovereignty. **PeroOCR**³ made some modules and models available as open-source, but this does not include any training functionalities. Finally, to the best of our knowledge, **eScriptorium** [6] is, apart from

² <https://teklia.com>

³ <https://pero-ocr.fit.vutbr.cz>

OCR4all, the only fully open-source GUI-based solution covering the entire text recognition workflow. However, as of now all automatic main steps are exclusively performed by Kraken, which differs fundamentally from our approach.

We conclude that there is a multitude of performant solutions for individual steps of the ATR workflow freely available, but there is a lack in open-source systems that focus on the easy integration and combination of said solutions.

3 OCR4all – Philosophy and Legacy Version

From the beginning, the main goal of OCR4all was to enable non-technical users to perform ATR on challenging material completely on their own obtaining high-quality results in the process. In this chapter we briefly cover the legacy version of OCR4all, but before that, we take a look at its underlying philosophy, which differs considerably from that of comparable approaches.

3.1 Philosophy

In contrast to most comparable tools OCR4all focuses on the integration and combination of various powerful open-source ATR software and we only selectively develop additional individual solutions. This frees up resources that can be invested in the further development and maintenance of the core software thereby increasing flexibility, future-proofing, and sustainability. Experience to date, not least within the OCR-D project, has clearly shown that there is not “one best universal workflow”, but that various partial solutions have different strengths and weaknesses and that the best possible results can usually be achieved through their flexible combination. This does not only apply to the technical implementation, but also to existing resources, especially available models. Last but certainly not least, OCR4all follows a very strict full open-source policy.

3.2 Legacy Version

OCR4all was developed as part of the Narragonien digital project which aimed to create a digital edition of the early modern classic “The Narrenschiff” by Sebastian Brant. Incorporated tools initially included OCRopus for binarization and deskewing, Calamari for text recognition and model training, Kraken for fully automatic layout analysis as well as LAREX for interactive layout analysis, visualization, correction, and ground truth production.

The project focused on processing a manageable amount of early prints, though with very high demands in terms of quality resulting in the need to invest considerable manual effort. This approach proved to be highly effective as an extensive evaluation on early prints showed recognition accuracies of considerably over 99% on character level [10]. Despite this focus, even the legacy version already performed well on tasks requiring a higher degree of automation or when applied to handwritten material resulting in a wide application in various projects.

Fig. 1. OCR4all system architecture including services and processes.

4 OCR4all – Version 1.0

Due to the constantly evolving needs and demands on such platforms as well as the rapid developments in software engineering best practices, we decided to go for a full reimplementaion of OCR4all. Fig. 1 shows an overview of the system whose various components we will explain in detail, starting from the general architecture and tech stack, to data management, and finally the different modules.

4.1 System Architecture and Tech Stack

To ensure scalability and to ease the addition of features the development is focused on modularity and composability. This is supported by the use of a distributed infrastructure and a strict separation of backend and frontend. The Java backend is based on the Spring Boot framework and uses a REST API for communication. Service provider technology is used to easily integrate third-party solutions. The frontend tech stack is centered around the current Vue.js ecosystem. All advanced editors (LAREX, NodeFlow, see below) are integrated as reusable components allowing easy future standalone usage if desired.

4.2 Data Formats and Data Management

OCR4all supports all commonly used image formats as input. Dedicated processors to import images from PDF files will be available soon. During the processing of the data the PAGE XML files store the collected data on page level. In

addition, the overall progress of each project is represented using a METS file which contains information about the processing history, providing a transcript of the generation history for all results ensuring traceability and transparency as well as further use in digitization workflows of libraries and archives. Regarding the output, suitable OCR-D processors accompanied by some in-house developments offer a rich selection of formats. Apart from the working formats PAGE, and METS this includes PDF, Word, ALTO, and TEI.

At all stages the users are always in full control of their own data. Every final and intermediary results can be viewed and freely exported at any time. In addition, all projects, workflows, models etc. can be freely shared amongst users using in-tool data management (cf. Sec. 4.3).

4.3 Modules

In this section we take a closer look at the most important modules regarding the practical usage of OCR4all, i.e. data management, the incorporation and application of various ATR solutions, the visualization and correction of results, as well as training and evaluation.

Repository A core principle of OCR4all is the strict separation of data management and processing. To this end, each instance of OCR4all uses a centralized repository to store and manage most the data. First of all, the input images are imported and stored here to serve as the foundation for the creation individual (sub-)projects which can then be processed individually, for example as part of a teaching event or similar. In addition, all models, workflows, as well as datasets for training and evaluation (see below) can be made available via the repository and, if desired, be shared with other users.

OCR(-D) Processors and NodeFlow To offer a wide and up-to-date selection of processors we engineered interfaces based on the OCR-D specifications so that additional processors can simply be plugged in. To make the creation and adaptation of (complex) OCR-D workflows as easy as possible we implemented the advanced workflow builder “NodeFlow” (cf. Fig. 2), a visual graph based node editor which enables full customizability without the need for any knowledge regarding coding or scripting. Apart from strictly linear workflows for productive use it is also possible to create so-called “branched workflows”, for example to compare different or models.

Naturally, it is also possible to add non-OCR-D processors in a very straightforward manner using dedicated containers and the well defined Java Service Provider interfaces. This openness towards different technologies does not only result in a broad selection of solutions for any given step of the workflow at this moment, but also ensures flexibility and sustainability in the future.

LAREX allows the visualization and editing of pretty much all results and partial results including region types, region and line polygons, baselines, the

Fig. 2. Example workflow in NodeFlow consisting of different processors, some with expanded settings view (left), and the corresponding processor selection GUI (right).

reading order as well as the text recognition result. In addition, different results for the same page can be compared by viewing them side by side.

Just like OCR4all, LAREX was reimplemented from scratch based on the same modern modular tech-stack (Spring Boot + Vue.js). Since LAREX relies on the official PAGE core libraries it is one of the very few tools that supports the full range of PAGE functions while always outputting fully valid and well-formed PAGE. Finally, in contrast to earlier versions of LAREX and most comparable tools, the new version now works as a true XML editor which manipulates the XML instead of always recreating it, possibly risking losing information.

Datasets, Training, and Evaluation Naturally, the far-reaching correction options of LAREX can also serve to produce GT for training and evaluation. So-called “datasets” contain sets of images and corresponding GT which can be collected from different projects, if desired by using the tagging functionality, or imported from external sources. Datasets can be viewed and edited in LAREX and be processed by workflows followed by an automated evaluation of the results. Trained models can be applied to and evaluated on further material as well as shared with other users via the repository.

As first solutions for training we focused on Calamari for text recognition and evaluation as well as Kraken for layout analysis. However, the well-defined, general, and abstract interfaces allow for an easy incorporation of additional solutions for training and evaluation in the future.

5 Working with OCR4all

In this chapter we focus on the practical application of the technical solutions described above. Before we discuss some typical use-cases and application sce-

narios, we first take a look at the two general processing modes, i.e. the stronger guided *base mode* and the more exploratory *experimental mode*.

5.1 Base Mode

This mode offers a rather strongly guided, linear workflow which can easily be operated independently by any given user. As of now the workflow focuses on offering selected solutions for any fundamental step, namely Tesseract and OCRopus for binarization, Kraken and Eynollah for layout analysis as well as Calamari and Tesseract for text recognition. Further solutions can easily be added, provided that they support the expected data formats. Users can either predefine their desired workflow and apply it at once to all pages of a project or go step by step, process just a subset of pages, check (and correct) the results and then continue to optimize the end result.

5.2 Experimental Mode

While being a little more complex to use this mode offers a lot more possibilities to explore, compare, and optimize since NodeFlow allows to freely play around with processors and models to define different workflows. Workflows can then easily be evaluated against each other in a qualitative (LAREX) and quantitative (datasets) manner to identify the most suitable workflow(s) for the task and the material at hand which can then either be shared or exported or the gained insights can be reused in the base mode. Naturally, the experimental mode is also suited to productive processing as workflows can either be executed at once or step by step after checking the results.

5.3 Application Scenarios and Use-Cases

OCR4all can now be applied to an even more heterogeneous selection of materials and use cases which we will discuss in the following. However, the best way to proceed is not always clear since it depends on the material at hand, the quality requirements of the users, available resources, etc.

Fully automatic mass full-text digitalization The full compatibility with OCR-D and the integration of the corresponding processors greatly improved OCR4all's capabilities with regards to mass full-text digitalization, e.g. in libraries and archives. The variety of processors combined with capabilities for quantitative and qualitative evaluation provides a powerful tool-kit to explore the workflows and models ideally suited to the material at hand. Naturally, the desired degree of workflow optimization is completely up to the users as it is always possible to simply rely on an existing (standard) solution, e.g. a full Tesseract-based workflow for maximum speed and throughput. Once identified, these workflows can then be applied either on the server running OCR4all or, if available, on a designated high performance cluster/server using the exported workflows and models as well as a standard OCR-D installation.

Flawless transcription of source material Located on the other end of the spectrum regarding the manual interaction is the high-quality transcription of texts, e.g. for the preparation of a critical edition, often expecting nothing short of a (near) perfect transcription result. While this forces the human transcribers to still check every single line of text, this process can be sped-up considerably by using a “iterative training approach” where the corrected data is regularly used to retrain models and process further pages with every increasing accuracy. Combined with comfortable to use tools and functionalities to support correction (synoptic line-based image/text views, freely configurable virtual keyboards, consistency checks watching over the entered codepoints, ...) the high-quality transcription becomes considerably faster and the risk for errors is minimized.

Minimizing manual effort while maximizing quality Not least due to the advance of quantitative research methods another application scenario is continuously gaining in importance where the goal is to apply computational methods to a large text corpus usually not requiring perfect text quality but still one that lies beyond the capabilities of available standard models. A concrete example for this is building a corpus of non-normalized text from medieval manuscripts to train word-embedding models (cf. [14] for details about the project). Since available mixed models usually cannot achieve the desired error rate there is a need to train manuscript-specific models based on corresponding GT which again is collected and combined to train mixed models to improve the out-of-the-box results. This has been shown to be very effective [11] and can comfortably be handled within OCR4all using the dataset and training functionality.

6 Conclusion and Future Work

With a completely reworked version of OCR4all we presented a fully open-source, flexible, and easy to use ATR tool which already offers a wide range of functions to effectively address the diverse requirements and challenges of a broad spectrum of use-cases differing considerably regarding materials, quality demands, and available resources for human intervention.

Yet, there is still a lot to do: After the recent release we expect a quickly rising number of users resulting in lots of feedback and feature requests which we plan to address as widely and as quickly as possible to further improve usability, user manuals, technical documentation, and of course the software itself. Regarding additional technical features, we plan the integration of further training modules, most likely Eynollah for layout analysis as well as TrOCR for text recognition. In addition, we aim for a better interoperability to digitization workflow tools often used in libraries. Concrete steps in cooperation with various institutions using Goobi⁴ are already underway. Finally, the implementation of an advanced resource management as well as allowing the connecting to existing security layers like OAuth and LDAP are important steps towards implementing OCR4all as a service for broad-based institutional usage.

⁴ <https://goobi.io>

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Arabic Handwritten Text Recognition using Advanced CNN-RNN Architecture

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Abstract. Optical character recognition (OCR) has attracted the interest of researchers in past years. Nevertheless, the development of learning architectures is lagging in Arabic handwritten text compared to other languages. This is due to the cursive nature of Arabic letters and the complex shapes each letter can have. In this paper, we evaluate the performance of CNN-RNN-based models for Arabic handwritten text recognition exploring variations of EfficientNet involving BiLSTM with and without attention mechanism. We propose using EfficientNetB3, which extracts features of input images, with three BiLSTMs for processing sequential features while improving the architecture performance by utilizing two attention heads. This allows the model to simultaneously focus on different parts of the input sequence. Lastly, the Connectionist Temporal Classification (CTC) layer is used to align the input sequence with the output sequence. The model performance, which is efficient compared to other CNN-RNN-based and transformer-based models, is tested on KHATT and AHAWP achieving cutting-edge results of character error rates of 17.26% and 0.28% respectively. To investigate its generalization ability, we ran the model on both datasets combined achieving a CER of 16.8% on the KHATT test set while 0.2% on that of AHAWP.

Keywords: OCR · Arabic handwritten text recognition · EfficientNetB3 · BiLSTMs · Attention · CTC · KHATT · AHAWP.

1 Introduction

Optical Character Recognition (OCR) is the process of converting text that is either printed or handwritten into machine-encoded text [1]. Although OCR has been around for many years, the desire to shift into a digital future through document digitization, coupled with the volume and importance of the documents involved, has forced researchers to look for fast and reliable OCR systems [2].

OCR of printed documents has seen great success in recent years [3] [4], however, handwritten documents are yet to find similar success [5]. Recognition of handwritten text has seen a lot of work recently, but only for languages with

well-defined character sets. Unfortunately, Arabic is not one of these languages; with a cursive nature, multiple writing styles, millions of words, and a handful of diacritics, the Arabic language is challenging for OCR systems [6].

The multiple writing styles and extensive vocabulary of the Arabic language pose significant challenges in dataset creation for Arabic OCR. Arabic datasets are designed to either focus on a limited set of words presented in various styles or to cover a broader vocabulary showcased in a few styles. The lack of standardized Arabic datasets has also been a challenge. However, efforts such as the KHATT [7] dataset attempt to address these issues by providing a more standardized resource for researchers in this domain. The authors in [8] highlight the main research trends and future directions for Arabic OCR, showing the role of datasets in advancing this field and expressing the deficiency of benchmark datasets for Arabic handwritten scripts.

To deal with the cursive nature of Arabic, some researchers adopted a global approach of Arabic language recognition [9], where words are treated as undivided units and are fed to feature extraction filters. In addition, there have been multiple algorithms aimed at character segmentation, including contour-based approach [10], template-matching [11], projection-based [12], and even some hybrid approaches [13]. Moreover, some researchers adopted the idea of segmenting characters and treating letters in different positions as different classes [14].

In this paper, we investigate the performance of CNN-RNN-based models for Arabic handwritten text OCR. In the ablation study, we explore versions of EfficientNet(B0, B1, B2, B3) with different combinations of BiLSTM and attention heads. We carried out three experiments for each model, using two datasets: KHATT [7] and AHAWP [31]. The first two experiments are done on each dataset separately. The last experiment combines both datasets in the training phase while evaluating each test set separately. This is done to evaluate the ability of each architecture to generalize when introduced to larger datasets.

Our proposed architecture¹ begins with EfficientNetB3, which extracts various image features, followed by three BiLSTM layers that process the sequence of characters in both forward and backward directions. Additionally, a multi-head attention mechanism with two attention heads allows the model to focus on different parts of the text simultaneously. Finally, a Connectionist Temporal Classification (CTC) layer aligns the input and output sequences without a pre-defined alignment, effectively decoding the features into readable text. We validated our model’s performance, using character error rate, on two datasets: KHATT [7] and AHAWP [31], where our model achieved state-of-the-art results of character error rate 17.26% and 0.28% respectively whereas, it achieved 16.8% on KHATT [7] test set and 0.2% on AHAWP [31] test set when trained on both datasets.

This paper is organized as follows: Section 1 is an introduction. Section 2 presents an overview of related work related. Section 3 describes the methodology of building the CNN-RNN-based systems. Section 4 describes the dataset, the

¹ The architecture code is uploaded to the following repository: <https://github.com/MohamedElsayed-22/EfficientNet-BiLSTM-Arabic-OCR>

applied preprocessing, and the proposed architectures. Section 5 discusses the results of the ablation study. Section 6 compares the proposed architecture with existing Arabic OCR systems. Section 7 concludes our work.

2 Related Work

2.1 Arabic Handwritten Word Recognition Systems

Authors in [9] demonstrated how crucial feature extraction is for Arabic OCR systems. The study highlighted how previous works have struggled with the feature extraction step, and illustrated how combining the output of multiple models, each with a different feature extractor, can increase the accuracy. achieving a recognition rate of 99.88% on the IFN/ENIT dataset [14]. One downside is that the results are only for 100 words/classes, and creating a general model must rely on a more analytical approach (i.e., character segmentation) instead of feature extraction filters.

Authors in [15] introduced a multi-stage HMM-based framework for Arabic handwritten text recognition. This system separates core character shapes from diacritics, representing core shapes through smaller sub-core units, significantly reducing the number of models required for training. The system employs multi-stream contextual HMMs, utilizing features from a sliding window and its horizontal derivatives as separate streams with distinct weights. Their approach demonstrated superior performance over traditional character-shape systems [16–19] across various text recognition tasks on both the IFN/ENIT [14] and KHATT [7] databases. One significant limitation is its dependency on the quality of preprocessing steps such as baseline and slant correction.

2.2 CNN-RNN-Based Arabic Handwritten Text OCR Systems

Authors in [20] employ a sophisticated deep learning methodology, using Multi-Dimensional Long Short-Term Memory (MDLSTM) networks developed in [21] with a Connectionist Temporal Classification (CTC) layer. The MDLSTM networks, capable of processing data in multiple directions, are adept at capturing the intricacies of Arabic handwriting. The training of the model on the KHATT [7] dataset involved complex preprocessing, including skew correction and height normalization, to improve recognition accuracy.

Authors in [22] also used MDLSTM [21] networks with a CTC layer. This model is trained on the KHATT [7] dataset. The key contributions include preprocessing strategies and data augmentation techniques. They focused on preprocessing, including pruning extra spaces and de-skewing text lines. The model’s architecture is carefully designed to handle the complexities of Arabic script.

Authors in [23] introduced Paddle-Paddle OCR as a full system multi-lingual. This system includes Arabic script recognition. It is a practical lightweight OCR model, that balances accuracy with model size. The initial model consists of three phases, text detection, direction classification, and finally text recognition.

The text recognition model is the most complex one. It uses a CRNN with MobileNetV3_small_x0.5 as a light backbone and reduces the dimension of the sequence feature to 48 to lighten the head.

2.3 Transformer-Based Arabic OCR System

Authors in [28] employed a transformer-based OCR architecture for recognizing 12 different fonts from historical documents and the KHATT [7] dataset. The architecture starts with Resnet101 as the feature extractor then a transformer consisting of two modules: an encoder and a decoder. Their model achieved high recognition rates, however, on a small subset of the dataset hindering the transformers' capabilities while making them prone to overfitting.

The authors extended their work in [29], where they used a Vision Transformer called BEIT as the encoder and Vanilla Transformer as the decoder while removing the CNN model used earlier. They also adopted a post-correction technique utilizing Word Beam Search Algorithm and BERT model for auto-correction. The training data subset was larger than the previous one, however, it still needs to be extended. The proposed architecture is considerably complex.

In later research, authors in [27] significantly improved Arabic OCR using Transformer-based architectures. They introduced two innovative models: the Transformer Transducer [30] and the standard sequence-to-sequence (Seq2Seq) Transformer. These models are designed to overcome the limitations of traditional recurrent neural networks. By employing pre-trained Transformers for both image understanding and language modeling. The inclusion of beam search techniques succeeds in improving accuracy, however, they increase decoding time.

3 Methodology

3.1 Learning Architecture

EfficientNet [32] introduces a groundbreaking approach to scaling network dimensions. Traditional methods scale *ConvNets* in depth, width, or resolution independently, leading to suboptimal performance. Such methods are applied to ResNet [33] where more layers are added to scale up from ResNet-18 to ResNet-200. Common scale-up methods are implemented by depth [33] or by width [34] mostly. EfficientNet utilizes a balanced method of scaling these dimensions. This is achieved through a compound coefficient methodology [32] that proportionally increases the depth, width, and resolution of the network.

Bidirectional Long Short Term Memory (BiLSTMs) As an extension of traditional LSTMs, BiLSTMs [36] can significantly improve learning performance on sequence data. Unlike standard LSTMs, BiLSTMs process data in both forward and backward directions, providing a more comprehensive understanding of the context in sequential data [37]. The authors in [37] also show how BiLSTMs excel in managing complex semantic processing tasks. This is crucial for tasks where context from both prior and subsequent data points is essential for accurate interpretation and prediction.

Attention Mechanism The concept of multi-head attention, introduced in [40], represents a significant leap in sequence modeling. Multi-head attention follows the concept of dividing the attention mechanism into multiple 'heads'. Consequently, the model simultaneously attends to different parts of the input sequence from different representational spaces [40]. In text recognition from relay protection drawings [43], multi-head attention plays a pivotal role in accurately classifying text images.

Connectionist Temporal Classification (CTC) The CTC [45] algorithm is designed to enable the training of sequence models without the need for pre-segmentation of the training data. Moreover, it provides a way to align input sequences with their target labels. It is mainly beneficial in tasks where the alignment between the input sequences and the output labels is unknown or variable, as in tasks that involve speech and optical character recognition.

3.2 Proposed model

The model we propose, shown in Fig.1, starts with EfficientNetB3. We have configured every layer of EfficientNetB3 to be trainable. This is to enhance its compatibility with Arabic script recognition. Then our architecture incorporates 3 BiLSTM layers. This arrangement is critical for analyzing the script in both forward and backward directions, a necessity given the contextual variability in the shapes of Arabic characters. The output dimensionality of these BiLSTM layers is set as follows: the first and third layers consist of 64 units each, while the second layer comprises 128 units. The features extracted by the BiLSTMs are then introduced to the multi-head attention, allowing for better handling of the input sequence and focusing on multiple points at once. The multi-head attention in our architecture consists of two heads each of key vectors of dimension 128. CTC is the final layer, which automatically segments and deals with the output of the multi-head attention to decode the output to give the prediction.

Fig. 1: Proposed learning architecture.

4 Experimental Work

4.1 Datasets

KFUPM Handwritten Arabic Text (KHATT) The KHATT [7] dataset is a comprehensive resource for Arabic handwritten text recognition research. It consists of 1000 handwritten forms contributed by 1000 different writers. In this paper, we worked on the unique text line images part of the dataset, which consists of 4837 in the training set, 967 in the test set, and 940 in the validation set. A sample of the data is shown in Fig. 2. We did further segmentation pre-processing and filtering on the images allowing better handling of the data to the model to avoid inappropriate lengthy input sequences.

Fig. 2: KHATT [7] dataset Samples

Arabic handwritten alphabets, words, and paragraphs per user dataset (AHAWP) The AHAWP [31] dataset, in which 82 users anonymously participated, covers 65 formats for 28 Arabic letters varying between having the letter at the beginning, middle, and end of the word. The dataset consists of 53199 alphabet images, 8144 word images, and 241 paragraph images. A sample from the dataset is shown in Fig. 3. Since there is no standard split, we divided the images at random into 80% for training, 10% for testing, and 10% for validation.

Fig. 3: AHAWP [31] dataset Samples

4.2 Pre-processing

After segmentation and filtering, the preprocessing steps, as shown in Fig. 4, involve five main stages for dataset preparation. Initially, image samples are converted to JPEG format to standardize their extension across datasets. Following this, grayscale conversion is applied, and images are binarized using a threshold of 127 pixels: pixels ≥ 127 become 255, and pixels < 127 become 0, this is done to achieve noise reduction and simplification of the samples for model compatibility. Color inversion is performed to facilitate resizing operations.

Given the Arabic script’s right-to-left reading orientation versus the left-to-right sequence used by the model architecture, image samples are mirrored horizontally. This ensures correct mapping of letter shapes to their machine-code equivalents without impacting learning processes. Thus, we enhance model performance by aligning image segment sequences with ground-truth expectations.

Finally, we resize all samples according to the experiment implemented. The dimensions are 172×62 in training AHAWP [31] dataset and 344×124 in the two other experiments. This is done to allow the CTC layer to process 12 segments in the first experiment and 44 segments in the second and third experiments.

Fig. 4: Data preprocessing steps

5 Ablation Study Results

On running different model architectures on the datasets, we incorporated an augmentation technique in which we added to each image sample in each batch three modifications with its augmented version. The first is a shear transformation where the shear transformation range is randomly picked between -0.3 and 0.3 for the horizontal and vertical axes. The other two modifications are adding random contrast and brightness changes. These sample images are temporarily generated in each training step. The augmentation is done using TensorFlow for the contrast and brightness changes while TensorFlow Addons for the shear transformation. we implemented a learning rate schedule using the *CosineDecayRestarts* schedule from TensorFlow’s Keras API to optimize the training process. The `initial_learning_rate` is 0.001, `first_decay_steps` is set to 5000, `t_mul` is 2, `m_mul` is 0.9, and `alpha` is set to 0.01.

We conducted five experiments to explore the different architectures under study. We made combinations of the CNN-based models, which are EfficientNetB(0, 1, 2, 3) with the RNN-based models utilizing BiLSTM with and without attention mechanism. In addition, each architecture is trained three times: once for the KHATT [7] dataset, another one for the AHAWP [31] dataset, and the final training is done on both datasets combined. In the final one, the model is evaluated on each dataset test set separately to verify its generalization ability.

To evaluate the performance, we used the character error rate (CER), also known as Levenshtein’s distance [47]. The results of the experiments are shown in table 1.

6 Discussion

As shown in Table 2, our proposed model, which consists of EfficientNetB3 as the CNN part and BiLSTM with Attention mechanism as the RNN part, achieved state-of-the-art results on both the KHATT [7] and AHAWP [31] datasets compared to other Arabic OCR systems. The dataset of AHAWP [31] is relatively

Table 1: Different Architectures Character Error Rate (*CER*)

Model Architecture	KHATT	AHAWP	Trained on Both	size
Eff.NetB3 and BiLSTM	31.6%	6.79%	30.15%, 4.99%	12.04M
Eff.NetB0, BiLSTM, and Attention	21.04%	0.81%	20.88%, 0.55%	5.317M
Eff.NetB1, BiLSTM, and Attention	19.23%	0.57%	18.87%, 0.34%	7.842M
Eff.NetB2, BiLSTM, and Attention	18.2%	0.4%	17.6%, 0.26%	9.1M
Eff.NetB3, BiLSTM, and Attention	17.26%	0.28%	16.8%, 0.2%	12.182M

new. Thus, it was not used against an OCR model. Our experiments are the first to be applied to this dataset where we achieved a character error rate of 0.28%.

In comparison with Momeni and BabaAli [27], the better performance is mainly driven by our segmentation, augmentation, and filtering done to the dataset mentioned before. Although these modifications did not make a tangible difference in the (*CER*) on the KHATT [7] dataset, our model (EfficientNetB3, BiLSTM, and Multi-head Attention heads) is lighter compared to their architecture. The transformer with cross-attention they propose in [27] has a parameter size of 153.1 M whereas, our best-performing model has a parameter size of 12.182 M making it less than one-tenth of their model.

Table 2: Comparison of our best-performing architecture to others on the KHATT dataset

OCR System	Architecture	CER
Mahmoud et al. [7]	HMM	53.87%
Ahmed and Fink [15]	HMM	41.21%
Ahmad et al. [20]	MDLSTM	24.2%
Ahmad et al. [22]	MDLSTM	19.98%
Momeni and BabaAli [27]	Transformer with cross-attention	18.45%
Our Architecture	Eff.NetB3, BiLSTM, and multi-head attention	17.26%

7 Conclusion

In this paper, we evaluate the performance of CNN-RNN-based models exploring variations of EfficientNet involving BiLSTM with and without attention mechanism for Arabic handwritten text recognition. We validated our method on state-of-the-art datasets: KHATT [7] and AHAWP [31] achieving state-of-the-art results on them. As mentioned before, Arabic handwritten text recognition still needs further advancements. It requires introducing richer datasets with more words and different writing styles and fonts. Consequently, the proposed model can be generalized and perform better.

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DiffLBP: towards differentiable and explainable texture analysis for documents

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Abstract. The contemporary state-of-the-art in writer identification consists almost exclusively of supervised deep-learning models. This leaves many things to be desired when working with a few samples coming from the wild. In this paper we present DiffLBP, a differentiable neural network layer that implements the hand-crafted SRS-LBP texture feature extractor and implement it as a cascade of pre-initialised convolutional layers. This gives us an end-to-end differentiable pipeline of a model that needs no training and is not biased towards any dataset. We use static uncontextualized embeddings of textual image textures as an elementary entity of hand-writing style, as they can be combined freely and through gradient ascent they can effectively be reversed. Further more, due to the compact representation, we turn multiple radii LBP into a compact dense descriptor and allow for interactive pixel retrieval tools that help expert find high-level features of handwriting.

Keywords: Writer Identification · Paleography · Texture Analysis.

1 Introduction

Texture analysis methods have a particular use for Document Image Analysis (DIA), with writer identification being a typical example of their application. As texture analysis can have various meanings, we consider it to be all methods where image descriptors with a receptive field much smaller than the image being analysed, are globally pooled, thus ignoring location of where in the image the descriptor was encountered. This definition is broader than the typical definition and includes all patch-based deep learning methods presently being perceived as the state-of-the-art.

1.1 Expert Assistance use cases

While this paper is written with paleographers in mind, it should be equally interesting to other experts analysing text images such as graphonomists. Writer identification methods have proven experimentally their potency with large properly curated datasets, but these experiments do not reflect many use-cases experts face. The vast majority of methods entails supervised learning of image

descriptors, which requires such datasets representing the data on which they will be applied. Further more, a minimum annotated dataset is always needed for performance evaluation of any method on the new domain. As there is no theoretical foundation proving the suitability and performance of any method to any specific domain/corpus, it is quite dangerous to employ such methods in an exploratory way. Without comprehensive experiments on the performance of a method on a corpus, the adoption of a method requires trust on the part of the expert. As the quality of text images differs dramatically under different acquisition modalities, this on its own makes most methods inapplicable on small heterogeneous collections of data, even in the case where only self-supervision and unsupervised methods are used. It is the case quite often, that experts don't know any identities of writers in the corpus they wish to analyse, and have good reasons to believe that these writers are not part of any other data collection. Even worst, they might not know how many hands are involved in a single page, and the notion of an elementary text-block such that a single hand is involved might be elusive. It is exactly in these, the most challenging scenarios, where experts need assistance from automatic methods. And in order to gain the trust from the scholar, methods need to explain their reasoning, they need to answer 'why' and they need to provide the scholar with understandable evidence.

2 Differentiable Local Binary Patterns

In order to modernize the SRS-LBP, make it more explainable, and integrating it to modern pipelines, we formulate it as a cascade of neural network layers which is fully differentiable¹.

2.1 SRS-LBP

In [9] Ojala et al. defined the LBP descriptor as a binary encoding of the comparison of a pixel to it's circular neighborhood. This allows a feature descriptor for a pixel's neighborhood to be encoded as a single integer and thus makes it trivial to obtain dense image descriptors. In the typical case, the name-space of the patterns is further compressed with the suppression of non-uniform patterns, and rotationally equivalent patterns are treated as the same-one, thus giving rotation invariance to the descriptor. The features are pooled into histograms by regions in the case of object classification [1] or globally when performing texture analysis.

The SRS-LBP (Sparse Radial Sampling Local Binary Patterns) is a pipeline developed for text texture analysis with writer identification in mind, at the time of it's publishing it achieved state-of-the-art performance [8] and has been employed unmodified for other tasks such as gender [3] and script recognition [7]. More recently it has been employed as a baseline for writer identification outperforming several deep learning methods [13]. The generic LBP descriptor was

¹ Code for the descriptor as well as the experiments is available on <https://github.com/anguelos/ptlbp>

modified by preserving all non-uniform patterns, because when the diameter of the sampling circle is larger than the stroke width, the patterns encode the shape of the letter skeleton. Furthermore, rotation invariance must not be employed as text is by nature anisotropic. As the goal of the SRS-LBP is to encapsulate information that is on the letters skeleton, the radii are much larger than any other variant, up to 12 pixels, while the sampled points are sparse, restricted to 8 regardless of the radius in order to keep the pattern lexicon small. The most remarkable innovation of the SRS-LBP descriptor is that instead of keeping the sign of the comparison between the central and the peripheral pixels, it encodes only significant differences that are thresholded. The threshold is computed by applying Otsu’s method on the differences occurring in the image; this exploits the bi-modal nature of text and makes the descriptors extremely robust against image degradation. The whole pipeline consisted of extracting the histograms of the SRS-LBP for all radii between 1 and twelve pixels, concatenating them as an global image descriptor, and reducing its dimensionality with Principal Components Analysis (PCA).

2.2 DiffLBP

The LBP feature extractor which computes histograms of patterns, can be realised by a cascade of Convolutional Neural Network Layers. The computational graph resulting from this approach can be seen in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. The computation graph of a single radius (histogram) visualised from pytorchviz. The input tensor along with the hand-crafted weights of the sampling layer and the encoding layer are marked as blue and the output histogram is marked as green. (best viewed electronically)

Point Sampling Layer The first layer is the layer that samples all the points on the circle. This layer is implemented as a 2D convolution layer with a pre-computed filter-bank. The filter-bank is of the dimensions $(n * c) \times c \times (2 * r + 1) \times (2 * r + 1)$ where n is the number of points to be sampled, typically 8, c is the number of input channels, typically 1, and r is the radius of the circle. The resulting tensor contains each peripheral pixel as a channel and the output width and height are cropped to only preserve valid pixels.

Comparison Layer The second layer consists of the comparison operator. For an implementation of the standard LBP, this layer could be integrated as part of the kernels in the point sampling but if a margin that takes the data into account is to be computed it must be a separate layer. In order to approximate the binary step function with a differentiable function, we use tanh. This layer has a single temperature parameter which by default is set to 0.1. Under the assumption images are valued in the range $[0, 1]$, we have implemented three different margins: a constant one set to .5, the 90th percentile of the differences pixels have to their circular neighbors, and the Otsu threshold [10] of the differences. In binary inputs there is little difference among them.

Binary Encoding Layer This layer is realised by employing a 1×1 convolutional layer, essentially a fully connected layer along the channels. As an input it receives bimodal distributed channels each one encoding the question "*is my neighbor significantly higher than me?*", while its output can be interpreted as the probability of a specific pattern occurring. Specifically, the weights are initialised to a sparse binary matrix BM sized $n \times 2^n$, where each row represents a relationship to a neighbor, each column represents a pattern, and each element is set to one if that neighbor participates to a pattern.

$$m = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^n x_i \tag{1}$$

$$y = x \cdot BM + m - (1 - x) \cdot BM$$

For every pixel's channels x the outputs y are computed as described in (1). Essentially, y has the negative edit distance of the pattern encoded by x and each on the binary patterns possible, incremented by one. The output y is passed through a softmax function with a temperature set by default to 0.1 in order to enforce a differentiable mutual exclusivity between different patterns for each pixel and favor a single choice for each pattern.

Histogram Pooling Layer Until now in the pipeline, pixels are analysed in a fully convolutional manner. The next step is to do global pooling in order to get a representation of the local texture regardless of where it occurs. In the original LBP descriptor, a histogram of the patterns made an extremely efficient representation. In our representation, the activations of the previous layer represent a soft one-hot encoding of the occurring patterns, so sum pooling along the width and height dimensions essentially constructs a histogram of the occurring one-hots. One of the most powerful aspects of the LBP features is that all pixels where there is no significant signal, are mapped to the 0 pattern, in the context of textual images; these are all the pixels whose neighborhood is either background-only or foreground-only. Ignoring the zero pattern makes the histogram invariant to the addition or removal of background pixels and thus totally insensitive to layout analysis and segmentation. While sum pooling essentially counts pixels occurring in the image, average pooling is equivalent to

computing the normalised histogram which is a representation that is invariant to the quantity of the signal, allowing for comparing samples coming from vastly different quantities of text. The temperature parameter of the encoding layers softmax function, allows us to control the trade-off between a smooth gradient and a accurate representation of the patterns histogram. While average and sum pooling are well differentiable and can be used in back-error probagation, a hard, non-differentiable alternative is also available. That allows more similarity to the original SRS-LBP descriptor and is much more efficient computationally as it also doesn't have use for the softmax of the encoding layer. For this pooling which we call "*discrete pooling*" we get the argmax along the channel dimension for each pixel, which gives the integer representation of each pixels pattern, and then we compute the histogram of these.

2.3 Compression Layer

In typical texture analysis, LBP patterns are scanned along circles with a radius of at most a few pixels [9]. Document texture analysis on the other hand benefits equally from much larger radii as well, because essentially patterns on radii larger than the stroke-width [4] and smaller than the letter size encode patterns equivalent to smaller radius patterns on the letters skeleton. As with the SRS-LBP, our pipeline encodes independently in parallel LBP on multiple, typically 12, radii. Their normalised pooled histograms are then concatenated to a single feature representation consisting of 254×12 features. A fully-connected layer weighing the features and compressing them to a more dense representation improves the representation for retrieval tasks. In the original SRS-LBP this was done with by getting the 200 most dominant components of the feature vectors. We use PCA components to initialise this linear layer [12] which can be further optimised. The Hellinger kernel is applied on the output features followed by an l2 normalisation. The resulting features are meant to be employed for retrieval with an l1 distance metric.

2.4 Unpooled LBP

While the pipeline mentioned above, performs well as a generic texture descriptor for textual images, the independence of the multiple radii make it hard to provide concrete argumentation for any finding that would be meaningful to experts such as paleographers. Paleographers and probably other domain experts, argue along the lines of specific ways of writing specific letters. As we sample eight points for every radius, there are 256 distinct patterns a pixel can have so the unpooled representation can be compressed to one byte per pixel per LBP radius or 12 bytes per pixel in total. This representation allows to merge all radii LBP into a single descriptor of 96 bits which encodes the binary fingerprint of any pixel. These descriptors are extremely cheaper than typical key-point descriptors which employ orders of magnitude more information, such as SHIFT [6] which employs 4096 bits. As the descriptor is binary in its nature, the most appropriate distance

for performing retrieval is Hamming distance which happens to be extremely computationally efficient.

Further more, up to 8 radii the descriptor can be encoded as a single long integer. Searching for an exact match on 1 Gigapixel can be done in 0.8 ± 0.02 seconds using `numpy`² on a single core of an Intel E3-1505M. While searching for similar patterns with a Hamming distance lower than eg. 3, can be done in 2.53 ± 0.028 seconds for a reasonably rare pattern while in the worst case where all pixels match, it can be done in 3.59 ± 0.047 seconds. Speeds like this make real-time searching across large images in real time feasible and open the way for designing interactive tools. In Fig. 2 we can see a specific unpooled pattern and the most similar patterns retrieved in an image.

Fig. 2. Pattern [193, 192, 192, 192, 192, 208, 208, 178] and similar point in a small corpus. The circles indicate the radius of the patterns and their color indicates how many of the radii agreed.

3 Experiments

The main goal of our experiments is to assess the performance of the DiffLBP implementing text-style features, we focus on writer identification as it is the most studied and representative problem in this category of problems. The employed pipelines do not contain the usual preprocessing steps, such as binarization, layout analysis, etc. because comparing to the state-of-the-art is not the target of our experiments. In Fig. 3 indicative samples from the datasets used can be seen.

3.1 Writer Identification 2013

The first experiment was performed on the ICDAR 2013 testset [5]. The problem was modeled as a retrieval problem and the post-processing pipeline used is the same as in [8]. The only learning involved in the experiments is the PCA

² Fast Hamming distance requires `bitwise_count` which at the moment of writing was only implemented in the experimental `numpy` version 2.0.0rc2

computation. In Table 1 we can see how DiffLBP performs in different retrieval modalities. As this dataset is perfectly binarized, the comparison modalities and the temperature parameters of the descriptor don't affect the outcome significantly.

Table 1. DiffLBP features on ICDAR 2013 Writer Identification

Language Mode	DB Size	Query Size	Replicates	Top 1 Acc. %	Top 5 Acc. %
English only	250	250	2	95.4 ± 0.200	98.0 ± 1.200
Greek only	250	250	2	97.8 ± 1.000	99.4 ± 0.200
Cross-language	500	500	2	69.6 ± 3.200	85.8 ± 1.800
Leave one sample out	750	250	4	96.7 ± 0.954	98.7 ± 0.995

3.2 Historical Fragment Segments

In order to see the performance of the DiffLBP features in supervised learning and challenging historical data, we employed them on a larger dataset, and framed the problem as supervised metric-learning of vector embeddings. We employed the test-set from the ICFHR 2021 competition [13], but as the official test-set is significantly different from the train-set [11], we partitioned once for all experiments the public test-set writers into a work-set and a test-set. The work-set contains 852 writers contributing 14,786 samples and the test-set contains 300 different writers contributing 5,233 samples. In every experiment fold, we separated the work-set into 752 writers for the train-set and 100 writers for the validation set used for early-stop, learning-rate scheduling etc.. In all cases we used a triplet loss with hard negative mining. In Table 2 we can see three model variants used. The first model is a single linear layer of 3072×200 parameters followed by the SRS-LBP [8] normalizations on the outputs and an L1 distance is employed for both training and inference. The second model is a single linear layer of 3072×200 as well, but without any normalisations and an L2 distance for both training and inference. The third model has four linear layers with a tanh non-linearity between them and an L2 distance. Both linear layers were initialised with PCA. While the model implementing the SRS-LBP performs remarkably better when initialised, during optimization the advantage dissipates. The normalizations applied before the loss, produce numeric instability which makes training of the first model harder.

Table 2. ICFHR 2021 test-data performance

Model	Init.	Distance Norm	Init test-set mAP %	test-set mAP %
Linear SRS	PCA	L1	26.84	54.28
Linear	PCA	L2	21.372	55.08
Deep	He	L2	20.37	56.72

Fig. 3. Three samples from HisFrag20 dataset and one from the 2013 WI Dataset

4 Conclusions

Discussion This work was motivated by the need to improve texture analysis explainability. In many cases we encounter, there is no ground-truth of any kind for the specific domain and scholars have questions instead of answers. In these cases explaining the biases of deep networks when used in knowledge transfer to paleographers who want to become agile in digital methods is often counter productive. Paleographers in those scenarios can not be confronted with similarity measurements, even heatmaps, while they evoke the imagination as to where in an image those similarities come from, they don't always explain why. Finding few localised measurements that are characteristic is much closer to the argumentation they expect. Unpooled LBP descriptors are much closer to the way of reasoning they already familiar with as the unambiguously evoke examples and counter-examples. It is why unpooled LBP in our opinion can better be used in software that lets the paleographers in the driving seat while assisting them with quantifiable and falsifiable suggestions. Further more the binary encoding of patterns makes each specific unpooled descriptor unambiguously serialisable as a few bytes. In this respect they are very similar to IP addresses, they are also easily understandable through their visual representation. This in its turn allows scholars to trivially store, share, evoke specific descriptors that allow to instantly retrieve and isolate paleographical features in a transparent and reproducible manner.

Future work Bianconi and Fernandez in their study [2] demonstrated that most LBP patterns are by construction extremely improbable, regardless of the input image structure. While rotation-invariance and uniformity-compression are sub-optimal for textual information, the backward gradient mechanism can be used to remove extremely improbable patterns experimentally. Removing these patterns would allow for significant memory and computational resources which would make the descriptor quite more efficient both in its differentiable and non-differentiable form, while compressing any feature representation based on the descriptor. Such a compression would make tractable generalising the descriptor to inputs of multiple channels. DiffLBP can be used to compute texture-similarity losses in text image generation. There are other texture descriptors that are equally interesting for documents such HOG which are not to hard to differentiate implementing them and comparing them to LBP could be interesting.

Limitations In comparison to traditional LBP descriptors, the fully differentiable descriptor employs an image channel per pattern. This makes feature generation much more demanding in memory if a backward step is needed. In learning free experiments, lowering the temperature parameter of the softmax, tends to provide a marginal increase in performance. This implies there might be a trade-off between differentiability and performance.

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Behind the Smoke: Misleading mistakes on the Tobacco3482 Document Benchmark

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Abstract. Tobacco3482 is a widely-used document classification benchmark dataset. However, our manual inspection of the entire dataset uncovers widespread ontological issues. We analyze the mistakes of a top-performing model made and found that 35% of the supposed mistakes are not actually mistakes. Rather, the model predicted alternative valid labels or was presented with images that do not belong to any of the dataset’s categories. Additionally, we report the incorrect label rate and instances of personally identifiable information (PII) discovered during our manual inspection.

Supplementary material, including dataset annotations and code, is available at <https://github.com/gordon-lim/tobacco3482-mistakes>.

Keywords: Tobacco3482 · Document image classification · Dataset Quality · Label errors

1 Introduction

Document classification is a fundamental component of document processing pipelines used by organizations for efficient search and retrieval [5]. Recent advances in document classification have demonstrated continual improvement in performance on the Tobacco3482 document image dataset [1, 6, 12, 15]. However, growing body of research on dataset quality casts serious doubt on the usefulness of many benchmark datasets for evaluating model performance. [2, 7, 8, 17]. Notably, ImageNet [3] has been found to have labeling issues, including incorrect labels and images that should be assigned multiple labels [13, 14]. Such issues destabilize benchmarks and make low capacity models seem less performant than they are [14]. To our knowledge, no studies have yet quantified the extent of label issues in the Tobacco3482 dataset. This short paper presents the first examination of the dataset for labeling issues. To contextualize the impact on model evaluation, we analyze the mistakes of a top-performing transformer-based document image classification model and found that 35% of the so-called mistakes were actually valid alternative labels or images that were not represented by any of the dataset’s labels.

Fig. 1. Example documents in Report category Traditional report examples are boxed in black. These documents have a structured format with sections such as introduction, methodology, and results. Ambiguous report examples are boxed in blue (left: Grant application detailing research proposal; right: Status summary for a product quality project) Mis-labeled report examples that are not reports (left: response to reviewers, right: presentation slides)

2 Tobacco3482 Categories

Tobacco3482 is a dataset of 3,482 document images, each labeled as one of 10 categories: *Advertisement (ADVE)*, *Email*, *Form*, *Letter*, *Memo*, *News*, *Note*, *Report*, *Resume*, or *Scientific*. These images were collected from the IIT Complex Document Information Processing (IIT-CDIP) Test Collection, which in turn sources its documents from the Truth Tobacco Industry Documents (TTID).³ Meanwhile, TTID is a database containing internal documents from major US tobacco companies, released as part of legal settlements [9]. These documents have one or multiple manual type annotations that include the 10 Tobacco3482 categories. Using TTID's API, we searched for Tobacco3482 documents by matching the Bates numbers in their filenames, resulting in the identification of 1,707 documents. Of these, 134 documents (3.8% of the dataset) have multiple Tobacco3482 category annotations. Yet, the Tobacco3482 dataset still assigns only a single label to these documents. Furthermore, there are no formal labeling guidelines

³ Available at: <https://www.industrydocuments.ucsf.edu/tobacco/> TTID was previously known as the Legacy Tobacco Documents Library.

reported by Tobacco3482, IIT-CDIP, or TTID, which raises concerns about the consistency and reliability of the labels within the Tobacco3482 dataset.

During an initial review of the Tobacco3482 dataset, we observed several instances of unusual categorization within the dataset. Here, we provide some examples in the *Reports* category (Figure 1) and refer the reader to more examples in our supplementary material. While some documents clearly fit the definition of a report, characterized by their structured format, such as introduction, methodology, and results sections, others fall into a *gray area* (in blue boxes). At the same time, there are also documents that were clearly misclassified as *Reports* (in red boxes).

3 Methods

Based on our initial review of the dataset, we exercised discretion in assigning new labels when category boundaries were unclear. We documented the process and provide a brief version of our guidelines, along with descriptive examples, in Table 1. Informally, we were lenient towards the given Tobacco3482 label when the documents somewhat fit the definition of the category (blue examples in Figure 1). However, we strictly removed the label when the document image was far from the definition (red examples Figure 1).

Given our corrected label annotations, we aimed to evaluate the impact on a model’s evaluation. Specifically, we wanted to analyse the model’s incorrect predictions and quantify how many of them were alternative valid labels or predictions made on images that did not belong to any of Tobacco3482’s label categories. We used a DiT model [11] from HuggingFace⁴, using RVL-CDIP [4] pre-trained weights. We selected this model because it is a top-performing model on RVL-CDIP, has not yet been benchmarked on Tobacco3482, and has accessible source code. To collect DiT’s mistakes on the entire dataset, we performed our evaluation using 4-fold cross-validation, achieving a 84.1% top-1 accuracy.

4 Results

Overlapping categories. We identified 583 samples (16.7% of the dataset) that should have multiple Tobacco3482 category labels. Figure 2 compares the overlap between different Tobacco3482 categories on our multi-label annotations. The *Memo* and *Report* categories exhibit the most overlap, as reports can often be written in memo format for communication purposes. The *report* and *scientific* categories also have a lot overlap, since reports can document results from scientific studies. Figures 3 and 4 provide examples of these overlapping categories.

⁴ https://huggingface.co/docs/transformers/en/model_doc/dit

Category	Description
ADVE	Media targeted towards a general audience to promote a product, service, or agenda. Can be found in newspapers. Excludes magazine covers and content drafts.
Email	Electronic mail, often including “Sent via electronic mail” or timestamps. Common features are “To/From”, “Subject”, “cc” fields, and digital attachments. Excludes HTML code.
Form	Documents with spaces (boxes, lines, etc.) to be filled in. Examples include registration forms, report templates, and data sheets. Excludes documents that print “Form” but do have fillable spaces.
Letter	Messages delivered on physical paper with physical addresses. Features include a letterhead, recipients name, address, salutation (e.g., “Dear xxx”), and sign-off (e.g., “Sincerely,”). Excludes <i>memos</i> using “letter” in its subject.
Memo	Documents addressed to an organization or person, often denoted by “To/From. They might state “Memo”, “Memorandum”, or “Correspondence”. Typical content include policy changes, meeting schedules, event invitations, recommendations, or actions. Excludes documents that print “File note” not addressed to anyone.
News	Articles resembling those in newspapers, typically with multiple columns and select font enlarged. They may also include newspaper clippings. Excludes scientific articles published in scientific news platforms.
Note	Handwritten or typed brief messages. Typically smaller than letter-sized paper and have minimal layout features. Excludes handwriting on other documents and <i>Reports</i> with “Note” in title.
Report	Formal documents presenting information, often with section headers such as introduction, methodology, and results. Topics can be scientific or non-scientific and might include data reports, findings, or series of events. May also presented using bullet lists or tables. Excludes documents that are primarily applications, requests, or proposals.
Resume	Formal documents containing personal career and/or education information, often titled “Curriculum Vitae”, “Resume” or “Biographical Sketch”. They include personal information like name, title, birth date, education, and professional experience.
Scientific	Documents containing scientific knowledge, typically written by scientists, often featuring scientific terms, mathematical formulas, and section headers like Abstract. Examples include research papers, grant applications, and project reports. Excludes business reports and product development reports.

Table 1. Guidelines and examples illustrating how we assigned new labels for the Tobacco3482 dataset.

Label errors. We also report 409 label errors, i.e., a 11.7% label error rate. This consists of 258 labels that matched none of our newly-assigned labels, i.e., mis-labeled. As well as 151 documents images that do not fall within the any of Tobacco3482’s label category. We present examples in Figure 5.

DiT Mistakes. Following the above, we found that of the 554 so-called mistakes made by the DiT model on Tobacco3482, 196 of them were not actually mistakes. Specifically, in 147 instances, the model predicted an alternative valid label from our multi-label annotations. Additionally, in 49 instances, the model faced the unfair and impossible challenge of predicting an *unknown* label. If we consider these *mistakes* as correct, the DiT model’s accuracy would increase to 89.7%. This marks a 5.7% improvement from the original 84.0% accuracy and brings it closer to a more recent method that achieved 90.7% accuracy using four times more parameters [15].

Fig. 2. UpSet plot [10] of multi-label Tobacco3482 category annotations. A majority of the documents with multiple labels are documents that are both *Reports* and *Memos*.

Label: *Memo*
Also: *Report*

Label: *Report*
Also: *Memo*

Label: *Report*
Also: *Scientific*

Label: *Scientific*
Also: *Report*

Fig. 3. Overlap of *Memo* and *Report* categories. Both are reports written in memos.

Fig. 4. Overlap of *Report* and *Scientific* categories. Both are reports on scientific studies.

Sensitive information. Finally, we report a notable presence of personally identifiable information within *Resume* category (see Table 2) including 9 SSNs. This means 7.5% of Tobacco3482 of the 120 Resume documents contain an SSN, which is close to the 7.7% reported by Larson et al. in the RVL-CDIP dataset [8]. This raises ethical concerns regarding the dataset’s curation.

5 Discussion, Future Work and Conclusion

This short paper represents a first effort to measure the extent of label errors in the Tobacco3482 dataset, adding to the relevant literature alongside papers

Count	Entity
SSN	9
Date of Birth	62
Place of Birth	28
Marital/Spousal Status	18
Parental/Children Status	12
Citizenship	18
Sex/Gender	3

Table 2. Counts of sensitive information in Tobacco3482

that do the same for other datasets, such as RVL-CDIP [8]. We also present early evidence showing how such errors can make model accuracy scores on these benchmarks misleading, as many mistakes were not actually mistakes. As model performance approaches near-perfect levels ($>95\%$), it is crucial that these accuracy metrics reflect a model’s ability to learn meaningful features seen in the real world, rather than spurious features in the dataset.

Future work will build on our work here by benchmarking more models on Tobacco3482 after addressing the issues we have documented, such as by using multi-label accuracy [16] and removing label errors. Additionally, we plan to apply the same analysis to RVL-CDIP, as the paper highlighting errors in RVL-CDIP has not yet conducted benchmarking that takes these issues into account.

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Fig. 5. Label errors in Tobacco3482. Tobacco3482 labels are shown in black. The top two rows show examples with *unknown* labels (not one of Tobacco3482 labels) and suggested labels in blue (where applicable), while the bottom two rows show examples with *mis-labels* and corrected Tobacco3482 labels in red.

